

UNIVERSITY OF

Global Health

EQUITY

STRATEGIC PLAN

2021 - 2025

UNIVERSITY OF GLOBAL HEALTH EQUITY (UGHE)

The University of Global Health Equity (UGHE) has an ambitious mission to train professionals at various levels in global health equity to address the global disease burden on the continent and beyond.

JOIN US IN OUR MISSION TO

The background of the entire page is a photograph of three graduates in black gowns and caps walking away from the camera down a hallway. The hallway has light-colored walls and a brick pillar. The graduates are seen from behind, and their caps are being adjusted. A large, semi-transparent white rectangle is overlaid on the top half of the image, containing the main text. On the left side of the white rectangle, there are two overlapping red arrows pointing towards the right.

TO TRAIN

**THE NEXT GENERATION
OF GLOBAL
HEALTH LEADERS**

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ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CAC	Community Advisory Council
CHSM	Community Health & Social Medicine
CNM	Center for Nursing & Midwifery
COVID-19	Corona Virus Disease-2019
DVC	Deputy Vice Chancellor
ELT	Executive Leadership Team
GHCD	Global Health Care Delivery
HRH	Human Resources for Health
M&E	Monitoring and Evaluation
MBBS	Bachelor of Medicine, Bachelor of Surgery
MERS	Middle East Respiratory Syndrome
MGHD	Master of Sciences in Global Health Delivery
OHC	One Health Collaborative
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy
PIH	Partners In Health
RNEC	Rwanda National Ethics Committee
SARS	Acute Respiratory Syndrome
SSA	Sub-Saharan Africa
ToR	Terms of Reference
U5M	Under-5 Mortality
UGHE	University of Global Health Equity
VC	Vice Chancellor

Preface

BY THE VICE CHANCELLOR

Agnes Binagwaho, MD, M(Ped), PhD

The University of Global Health Equity is a cutting-edge institution based on the notion that equity in health cannot be achieved without equity in education for health sciences. As a leading independent, innovative university, we are shifting the paradigm of health sciences education by training future leaders to be skilled, flexible, and competent to address dynamic, complex global health needs at all levels, while prioritizing equity through this process.

We are proud of our unique educational approach that both champions health as a human right and as a pillar of development and creates solutions to cure and treat the disparities in access to quality modern health services at all levels of services. This Strategic Plan outlines how UGHE will continue to train future global health leaders to contribute, build, repair, strengthen, and manage resilient health sectors to provide equitable quality services.

It will also guide how we grow our university and the way the whole UGHE family across the world will change the delivery of health services, and promote inclusion as well as diversity as we diligently strive to make a meaningful difference in Africa and beyond."

Ward

FROM THE BOARD CHAIR

Sheila Davis, DNP, ANP-BC, FAAN
CEO, Partners In Health

One of the reasons I created OnePIH was to illuminate the unique opportunity that UGHE provides for the global equity movement. A Global University based on the continent of Africa, to prepare the next generation of health providers to provide quality care--is fantastic.

That University as part of an organization with 11 geographically and contextually unique care delivery sites caring for millions of people every day, preferentially caring for those made most vulnerable, is transformational.

BRIEF PROFILE OF UGHE

UGHE PROFILE

UGHE at a Glance

The University of Global Health Equity (UGHE) is a private, not-for-profit fully accredited university. It is an initiative of Partners In Health (PIH), a global health and social justice organization with a mission to strengthen health systems and advance equity in global health care. In partnership with the Government of Rwanda (GoR), PIH and two foundations (Cummings and Bill & Melinda Gates Foundations), the first phase of the University was initiated in 2015. The GoR provided a strategic parcel of land in Burera District, tax waivers and critical infrastructure.

Rwanda's innovative approach to health care reform has driven perhaps the most dramatic improvements in population health and prosperity in the world. Through progressive education programs, experiential learning, and research, UGHE—enrolled its first cohort of medical students in 2019—with an aim to becoming a global hub for advancing and disseminating such innovations in health care delivery science and for cultivating a new generation of global health leaders capable of responding to crucial needs to help improve the social determinants of health for the vulnerable.

The University is based in Butaro Sector, of Burera District in the Northern Province of Rwanda. It is, 130 kilometres north of Rwanda's capital city, Kigali with a Liaison Office in Kigali. UGHE enjoys a unique regional, continental, and global influence in Global Health equity due to its governance and leadership with a demonstrable track record of outstanding research, academic excellence, community engagement and impact. It is deliberately located in a rural primary health care system setting, in order to provide outreach education that will better equip our students to meet the challenges they will be tasked with as they serve and develop health sectors where the lack of health professionals and the number of vulnerable are the highest a chance for students and lecturers to experience first hand community service and health care engagement as they learn and teach.

The design and location of UGHE's campus offer students diverse educational opportunities in both clinical and delivery settings. The campus was intentionally built to encourage communication and collaboration across programs, with pathways and nodes integrating common areas with labs and classrooms. Teaching spaces afford students an engaging and hands-on educational environment, while UGHE's proximity to Butaro District Hospital serving the local community reflects the University's commitment to experiential and problem-based learning. UGHE is located in Rwanda because of the country's impressive track record of health care delivery innovation, success in health systems strengthening, and commitment to reducing social, economic, and health inequalities.

Currently the University is offering a Master of Science degree program in Global Health Delivery (MGHD) with the following tracks: Gender, Sexual and Reproductive Health, One Health and Health Management, a one year, full-time degree program. UGHE is also offering a Bachelor of Medicine, Bachelor of Surgery (MBBS) and Master of Science in Global Health Delivery (MGHD) dual-degree program (MBBS/MGHD). In the next five year cycle, the new programs include: PhD (integrated basic medical sciences and Global Health Equity); Masters in Health Services Administration, Med Ed, Global CBE, Oncology Nursing, Nursing and Midwifery Leadership, MGHD program with concentration in Global Surgery, Healthcare ethics and law, Healthcare architecture, Health Financing; BSc program in Health Care Supply Chain Management; Executive Education programs (Nursing and Midwifery Leadership, Gender Equity and leadership as well as Healthcare Education Leadership (E-HEAL) and a new certificate program Health professional education. The Department for Arts and Culture in Global Health and Public Engagement will also be established.

UGHE Impact to date

70%

of UGHE's medical students cohort are female

516

learners taught by UGHE between 2015-2020

18

countries served by UGHE's MGHD alumni

38

countries represented by Executive Education learners

1. University of Global Health Equity website. www.ughe.org

2. Farmer PE, Nutt CT, Wagner CM, et al. Reduced premature mortality in Rwanda: lessons from success

UGHE

MISSION

To radically transform global health education and how health care is delivered around the world by training generations of health professionals who strive to deliver more equitable quality, and holistic health services for all.

UGHE

VISION

To be a leading university that strives to train the next generation of global health leaders with an emphasis of transforming them into change makers equipped with the skills to protect the most vulnerable and improve health outcomes and social systems.

UGHE

VALUES

- **Equity**
 - Inclusion and Diversity
 - Respect
 - Social Justice
 - Universal Health Care
- **Community-Based Education and Health Care**
- **Sustainability**
- **Cultural Humanity**
- **Integrity**
- **Innovation**

SCOPE OF THE STRATEGIC PLAN

This Strategic Plan sets out a framework to guide UGHE’s intervention priorities across the broad spectrum of its stated aspirations in 2021-2025.

It is underpinned by a detailed implementation plan, risk assessment, mitigation measures and implementation budget as well as a comprehensive capacity building plan.

2. INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

UGHE

In November 2017, the UGHE Board of Directors approved its first Strategic Plan for 2018-2022 that has acted as a foundational step in the development of the second Strategic Plan (2021-2025) that will be an enabler for UGHE to realize its priorities and assume its position as an internationally recognized University at which to study, teach, research, partner, and donate, all in service of the ideal of global health equity.

The approach taken in the preparation of the strategic plan was participatory. The new strategic plan formulation is grounded on the outcomes of a critical self-assessment process by the UGHE Board and Executive Leadership Team as well as faculty and staff who discussed extensively their ambitions to sustain their status as a World-class institution of higher learning in global health equity in tandem with national and international dynamics. It shall therefore facilitate the Board of Directors, Executive Leadership Team, students, staff, faculty, and Partners all experience the distinctive benefits outlined below:

- Global health equity perspectives;
- Commitment to community outreach, welfare and good health;
- Delivery of a top-notch international approach to students learning and professional/personal growth so that they can exemplify and support UGHE's mission;
- Transdisciplinary and high impact research;
- Diversity and inclusion;
- Inter-professional experiences that

contribute to global scholarly activities; and

- New and expanded partnerships and an enabling learning environment.
- Entrepreneurship and Management skills to enable our students to contribute, create and maintain the necessary environment to exercise the skills and the knowledge acquired at UGHE.

Throughout the UGHE strategic planning process, discussions were premised on the following areas:

- The UGHE Mission, Vision and Values.
- Perspectives, needs, and expectations of internal stakeholders and external partners.
- The high-level, overarching strategic goals.
- Key priorities, strategic initiatives, and action plans.
- Outcomes and Achievements.

Recognizing that Global Health Equity is a dynamic field, with constantly emerging and re-emerging global health threats and challenges, since its inception, UGHE has been undertaking impactful programs and initiatives that are mutually beneficial and have inculcated an environment for exchange of knowledge, skills and shared experience.

The University has successfully positioned itself as a unique institution on global health equity issues given its expertise in significantly addressing contemporary global health challenges.

3. SITUATION ANALYSIS

ANALYSIS

SITUATION

Overview

In November 2017, the UGHE Board of Directors approved its first Strategic Plan for the period 2018-2022 that underpinned the following strategic priorities:

- (i) Health and implementation Science Education;
- (ii) Research, policy, and advocacy in delivery Science;
- (iii) Services for global health professionals;
- (iv) Maximizing community impact; and
- (v) Building an enduring institution.

Since its inception and particularly during the period under the current Strategic Plan, it is noted that UGHE has “made a transformative impact” by creating a new generation of global health champions dedicated to the equitable delivery of health care in a resource-limited setting.

Table 1: Snapshot of strengths, achievements, major challenges, opportunities and an outline of the way forward.

Achievements	Major challenges	Opportunities	Way forward ¹
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ April 2015: MGHD was accredited. ■ 2016: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Established its center for Executive Education; ○ Introduced a portfolio of Executive Education Certificate courses. ■ 2017: MGHD Graduated its first cohort of part-time students. ■ 2018: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Full-time MGHD enrolled its first cohort; ○ Founding Dean of the School of Medicine; ○ Established its 1) School of Medicine 2) Institute of Global Health and the 3) Educational Development and Quality Centre. ■ 2019: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Inaugurated Butaro Campus; ○ Put in place the state-of-the-art training facilities, laboratories, and clinical simulation centre; ○ UGHE convened its inaugural One Health symposium bringing together clinicians, community health workers, farmers, environmentalists, policymakers, and researchers. ○ The MBBS/MGHD program received accreditation from the HEC and RMDC; ○ Established the Centre of One Health; ○ Inaugural class of MBBS/MGHD; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Dependence on external financial support, mostly philanthropists ■ Limited long-term sources of revenue streams to sustain the planned infrastructure expansion and new academic programs ■ Limited infrastructure capacity for training at the Butaro campus (as of 2021). ■ Infancy of UGHE and inherent challenges to meet expectations of partners. ■ Readiness of clinical teaching space. ■ Limited availability of expert Human Resources for Health in the local market. ■ Unexpected global challenges such as the COVID epidemic. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Dedicated and visionary leadership ■ Resilient and expert academic faculty ■ Partnerships and MoUs with leading universities ■ A unique vision and mission as a university that strongly believes in global health equity education ■ Partnerships with global philanthropists and donors ■ Strong linkage with the host Government ■ UGHE’s main focus on emerging global health needs to guide its training and research direction ■ Goodwill from the community due to UGHE proactive community engagement initiatives ■ Partnership with the Butaro hospital that provides opportunity for teaching, research and clinical practice 	<p>Academic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Maintain the quality and relevance of our existing programs; ○ Launch new programs at PhD, MSc, BSc, Executive Education and Certificate levels that are aligned to the current global health needs. <p>Research</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Spearhead research in innovative pedagogical practices, clinical practices, policy intervention, community priorities on diversity and inclusion, production of medical tools and drugs, mHealth, Clinical Technology, community engagement initiatives as well as medicine and therapeutics for existing and emerging diseases; ○ Prioritize research that will generate revenue to contribute to the financial sustainability of UGHE research activities; ○ Maintain and strengthen the Dean’s research grant initiative; ○ Attract research funding from regional and international funding institutions. <p>Community Engagement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Strengthen and mainstream the role of the Community Advisory Committee (CAC) in UGHE programs; ○ Local sourcing of materials from Butaro and neighboring communities; ○ Conduct entrepreneurship training of Butaro Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and cooperatives; ○ Develop and implement a UGHE structured community outreach plan; ○ Conduct community awareness campaigns on global health equity issues through ingenious and innovative approaches like competitions at Local and national levels; ○ Create jobs by contracting and sourcing from local suppliers. <p>Community Health</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Produce innovative educational programs that promote community-based approaches to improving health and building partnerships; ○ Conduct community-based participatory research (CBPR) focused on enhancing primary healthcare and community health systems in diverse contexts; ○ Collaborate with communities to establish advocacy efforts that advance access to equitable health services for underserved populations; ○ Partner with relevant stakeholders to tackle community health concerns and their social, economic, and commercial determinants; ○ Launch the Department for Arts and Culture in Global Health and Public Engagement.

(Footnotes) 1

Details are captured in subsequent section of the Strategic Plan with targets articulated in the Log Frame (implementation plan)

Achievements	Major challenges	Opportunities	Way forward1
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ UGHE hosted the Women Leaders in Global Health Conference for the first time in Africa and the third time in the world after London and Stanford; ○ Inaugural HAMWE Festival. <p>■ 2020</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Second Hamwe Festival hosted virtually; ○ Graduated its fifth cohort of MGHD students amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic; ○ Enrolled the second cohort of medical students; ○ UGHE established its 1) Centre for Gender Equity, 2) Centre for Nursing and Midwifery and the 3) Institute of Global Health Equity Research; ○ Launched its inaugural MGHD track in One Health program; ○ Hired and trained diverse staff in various disciplines; ○ Promoted an established reputation of being a world class research-driven university of global health equity education; ○ Strengthened its capacity to generate revenue from its partnerships and research agenda; ○ Finalized establishing its ICT infrastructure; ○ Submitted its proposal to start the following programs for approval; ○ Gender, Sexual and Reproductive Health; ○ Msc in Hospital Services Management. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Attractive and competitive compensation and benefits for staff and faculty; ■ A clear masterplan for land use as well as utilization and expansion of UGHE infrastructure; ■ UGHE brand image. 	<p>Equity and diversity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Catalyse intellectual discourse and cross pollination of ideas related on gender equity and diversity inclusion; ○ Mainstream gender equity and diversity inclusion; ○ Strengthen consideration for diversity and inclusion in UGHE infrastructure development. <p>Infrastructure development (Phase II)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Construction of Housing Facilities ○ Administration Office Space ○ Academic Facilities ○ Clinical Facilities ○ Recreational Facilities – Indoor and Outdoor ○ Event Facilities ○ Dining Facilities ○ Expansion of Butaro District Hospital ○ UGHE’s Institute of Global Health Equity Research ○ Masaka premises <p>People</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Conduct workload analysis; ○ Hire people from local communities to participate in UGHE project activities especially for blue colour activities; ○ Scale up the mix of diverse pool of talent from both in country and abroad; ○ Nurturing talent as a repository for future source of recruitment; ○ Scale up the use of visiting faculty, Interns, Volunteers and Fellows; ○ Conduct training needs assessments (TNA) and plans; ○ Put in place staff and faculty retention measures ○ Conduct staff and faculty satisfaction surveys ○ Implement UGHE staff and faculty performance management evaluation; ○ Conduct staff and faculty induction and refresher sessions; ○ Develop a succession plan; ○ Establish/improve staff welfare programs; ○ Introduce monetary and non-monetary rewards for best performing staff; ○ Develop and enforce an Office health and safety policy across the UGHE campus and offices; ○ Develop a UGHE employee handbook. <p>Financial sustainability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Expand existing funding opportunities and sources to address current and projected financial needs through 2025; ○ Package and market the strategic infrastructure investments funding requirements; ○ Develop new operating model for future financial mobilization and sustainability Develop a resource mobilization strategy.

Conclusion: The result from the Situation Analysis has been used to generate strategic initiatives that will guide UGHE interventions to achieve their strategic objectives. UGHE will seek to build on the achievements that have been registered during the implementation of its first strategic plan to propel it towards the realization of targets made in the next strategic plan. The implementation challenges shall be matters of focus to ensure their impact is minimized. Emerging opportunities will be exploited to gain an enabling teaching, learning and research environment, building on internal strength, continued goodwill and support from partners to deliver on its second generation strategic orientation.

4. STRATEGIC PRIORITIES

UGHE

STRATEGIC PRIORITIES

Our strategic priorities are;

1. Academic Excellence
2. Excellence in Research and Quality
3. Maximizing Community Benefit
4. Building an Enduring Institution

This Strategic Plan does not view the strategic priorities as distinct or linear domains, but takes cognizance of how the priorities are aligned with each other and mutually supportive. These priorities therefore provide pathways through which UGHE will navigate potential impediments and translate its vision into practical and actionable undertakings as highlighted in the following Sections.

STRATEGIC PRIORITY

1

a. ACADEMIC EXCELLENCE

UGHE envisages building on ongoing successful academic programs in Global Health Equity Education, reviewing and launching new ones with the objective of being a recognized Global Health University. Its success will be benchmarked on the highest international standards with dynamic curricula responsive to the 21st Century global health challenges. The planned programs will be at the level of PhD, Masters, Bachelors and Certificate levels as well as Executive Education.

Nurturing a culture of continuous improvement and strengthening the teaching and learning at UGHE requires fit-for-purpose academic quality initiatives aligned to the required standards for a 'unique' institution like UGHE that is founded on a philosophy to deliver global health equity education.

Strategic Initiatives:

The following Strategic Initiatives shall be implemented to achieve academic excellence:

Strategic Initiatives	Key Results Indicators (KRIs)
■ Launch new academic programs at PhD, MSc, BSc, Executive Education and Certificate levels, as well as the Department for Arts and Culture in Global Health and Public Engagement.	New undergraduate and post-graduate programs accredited and implemented with international pedagogical and clinical practice standards
■ Increase students' enrollment in existing programs.	
■ Strengthen the relevance and quality of academic programs.	
■ Strengthen and enforce standardized international practices in pedagogy and clinical practice for undergraduate and post-graduate training through the UGHE Education and Quality Development Centre	

STRATEGIC PRIORITY 2

b. EXCELLENCE IN RESEARCH AND INNOVATION

Research is central to a University's transformation process, and ultimately strengthening its impact and visibility nationally and internationally. UGHE has thus triggered a vibrant intellectual climate and funding that has stimulated all its faculty, staff and students to undertake relevant cutting-edge research. Under this new Strategic Plan, a lot more emphasis will be placed on research in high-impact areas to help in the achievement of the university's global health equity goals.

To harness the opportunities to reimagine healthcare and healthcare delivery, UGHE has established the Institute of Research to generate and promote innovative research and research training to augment its existing education programs with the goal to establish best practices in the education of health professionals as well as the development and delivery of health services and programs.

Strategic Initiatives

The following Strategic Initiatives shall be implemented to deliver evidence-based research, innovation, and knowledge exchange at UGHE:

Strategic Initiatives	Projected Outcome
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Spearhead research in education and training to investigate the implementation of innovative pedagogical practices and inform the development of effective and engaging education and training activities. 	<p>Strategically relevant research outputs on global health equity addressing practical community priorities, stimulating policy dialogue, providing a launch pad for generating income from knowledge (products and services)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Enhance research, policy, and advocacy to deliver high-quality, pioneering research activity that will inform and challenge policy and provide the foundation for persuasive, inspiring, and game-changing advocacy. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Conduct community-focused research addressing community priorities with particular attention to diversity and inclusion. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Prioritize research that will generate revenue to contribute to financial sustainability Initiate research that will lead to the production of medical tools and drugs to improve access to quality health care. 	

STRATEGIC PRIORITY

3

c. MAXIMISING COMMUNITY BENEFITS

UGHE will deliver community services through its academic undertakings embodied in the Community Health and Social Medicine (CHSM) programs as well as non-academic social economic transformation activities through community engagement initiatives.

I. Community Health and Social Medicine

Community Health and Social Medicine (CHSM) is premised on impacting the community through (i) education, research, advocacy, and action. (ii) Community health focused on studying and improving the physical and mental wellbeing of people in a specific geographic region, (iii) Social medicine which seeks to understand how health, disease and social conditions are interrelated.

Strategic Initiatives

The following Strategic Initiatives shall be implemented to enhance undertakings in Community Health and Social Medicine programs

Strategic Initiatives	Projected Outcome
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Produce innovative educational programs that promote community-based approaches to improving health and building partnerships. 	Active partnership between UGHE and the community to collaboratively address health, social and economic challenges with contextualized and evidence-based solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Conduct community-based participatory research (CBPR) to enhance primary healthcare and community health systems in diverse contexts. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Collaborate with communities to establish advocacy efforts that advance access to equitable health services for underserved populations. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Partner with relevant stakeholders to tackle community health concerns and their social, economic, and commercial determinants. 	

II. Community Engagement Program

UGHE Community engagement program will promote social-economic transformation of the community through various initiatives including entrepreneurship training, job creation, local contracting, sourcing of materials and contributing to social welfare like health insurance schemes and supporting the under privileged.

This will call for collective participation of all actors in the community towards addressing identified social and economic challenges. UGHE formed the Community Advisory Committee (CAC) representing the youth, women, the private sector, the health sector, community members with non-communicable diseases, the disabled, people living with HIV, and local leadership to be part of this transformational process.

Strategic Initiatives

The following Strategic Initiatives shall be implemented to enhance undertakings in Community engagement programs.

Strategic Initiatives	Projected Outcome
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Establish the Community Advisory Committee (CAC) and define their role in working with UGHE programs. 	A UGHE structured and operationalized community outreach plan
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Local sourcing of materials from Butaro and neighboring communities 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Entrepreneurship training of Butaro Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and cooperatives 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Conduct research to inform community engagement initiatives 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Develop a UGHE structured community outreach plan 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Conduct community awareness campaigns on global health equity issues through ingenious and innovative approaches like competitions at Local and national levels 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Create jobs by contracting and sourcing from local suppliers 	

STRATEGIC PRIORITY

4

d. BUILDING AN ENDURING INSTITUTION

UGHE strives to build on the success and momentum it has accumulated since its inception to create an institution that will thrive for the long term, UGHE's institutional values have been carefully crafted and reinforced. The University's Executive Leadership Team continue to be committed to providing rewarding careers to a diverse set of employees, rigorous planning for the future, and nurturing relationships with Board of Directors, partners, donors, and the community.

STRATEGIC PRIORITIES

STRATEGIC PRIORITY

4

BUILDING AN ENDURING INSTITUTION

I. Infrastructure Development

Building on the success registered in Phase 1, UGHE will scale up infrastructure development in line with its Integrated Master Plan by constructing new infrastructure, and maintaining existing infrastructure and facilities to make them commensurate with planned utilization through 2025. This will provide the required state-of-the-art infrastructure and facilities to enable an efficient and stimulating environment for learning, teaching, research and extracurricula activities at the University in tandem with its vision and mission.

Phase 2 will demonstrate agility in planning and delivering modern real estate projects informed by opportunities for consolidation and configuration to optimize available space and realize value-for-money with quality and fitness-for-purpose. It will also ensure the integration of information technology infrastructure to support content delivery in blended learning, teaching, research, communication responsive to the new reality in the age of COVID-19 and beyond.

This will be paramount in leveraging UGHE’s capacity to cope with the changing working pattern of the 21st Century as a world-class academic institution by availing the university community with learning, teaching and research resources as well as modern facilities. UGHE’s technological assets will in this phase, have in perspective the rapid developments and ensure agility to systematically plug in new systems to acquire, create, capture, store, retrieve, present and manage new information resources for use by the university community.

As of May 2021, preliminary development and compilation of project documents and plans of UGHE Butaro campus phase II expansion had been finalized.

The project inception report and the comprehensive project plan including the detailed project brief were under review and the masterplan had been completed. The design work was started to guide the construction firm that would be procured to execute the project.

Strategic Initiatives

Setting Strategic Initiatives for UGHE Infrastructure Development will include construction and expansion of the following facilities;

Strategic Initiatives	Projected Outcome
■ Housing Facilities;	An implemented Phase II of the UGHE Master Plan
■ Student And Staff Services;	
■ Administration Office Space;	
■ Academic Facilities;	
■ Clinical Facilities;	
■ Recreational – Outdoor and Indoor Facilities;	
■ Event Facilities;	
■ Dining Facilities;	
■ Recreational – Facilities Outdoor;	
■ Expansion of Butaro District Hospital;	
■ UGHE’s Institute of Global Health Equity Research (Masaka).	

STRATEGIC PRIORITY

4

BUILDING AN ENDURING INSTITUTION

II. People

UGHE values the role of its staff and faculty in the delivery of its mission and vision underpinned by an impactful long-term focus on talent, processes, and organizational development because the success of its programs and projects hinges on the quality of its academic, research, professional and support staff.

On this basis, UGHE envisions to continuously develop its People (Faculty and Staff) by attracting, recruiting, utilizing, rewarding, motivating, retaining, nurturing high caliber faculty and staff through implementing its human resource management and development policies as well as processes.

Strategic Initiatives

The following Strategic Initiatives shall be implemented to achieve the UGHE Human Resource Development aspirations:

Strategic Initiatives	Projected Outcome
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Identify, attract, utilize and retain high quality employees	A motivated, committed and high performing faculty and staff community
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Nurturing talent as a repository for future source of recruitment	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Achieve diversity by employing from local communities to support UGHE's development activities (where possible) to boost household incomes (gender, PWD, equity considerations)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Expand faculty and staff numbers to meet the increase in workload commensurate with UGHE projected expansion	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Scale up the use of visiting faculty, Interns, Volunteers and Fellows through structured partnerships with various institutions on both full-time and part time basis for staff and faculty	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">Sponsor UGHE faculty as interns and fellows under staff exchange arrangement with various institutions to increase their exposure and experience	

STRATEGIC PRIORITY 4

BUILDING AN ENDURING INSTITUTION

III. Financial Resources and Sustainability

The University will launch a drive to map, profile and onboard more partners in government, corporate and not-for-profit organizations to fund its planned projects, expand opportunities and resource funnels for growth while aligning resource utilization to strategic priorities within the framework of the Strategic Plan 2021-2025.

UGHE will also develop new business operating models and enhance its project portfolio mirrored on a pipeline of projects for its future financial mobilization and sustainability.

Strategic Initiatives

The following Strategic Initiatives shall be implemented to address UGHE resource challenges in the Short, medium and long term:

Strategic Initiatives	Projected Outcome
■ Expand existing funding opportunities and sources to address current and projected financial needs through 2025	Predictable revenue streams to sustainably support implementation of the Strategic Plan
■ Package and market the strategic infrastructure investments funding requirements that can appeal to philanthropists with an interest in global health equity.	
■ Develop new business models for future financial mobilization and sustainability (explore and develop new revenue streams including identifying more partners to share costs on specific projects and program; investments in revenue generating projects, research & consultancies)	
■ Resource mobilization strategy	
■ Develop a Resource mobilization strategy	

STRATEGIC PRIORITY 4

BUILDING AN ENDURING INSTITUTION

IV. Diversity and Inclusion

UGHE, being a global University with an international outlook has a wide spectrum of diversity. In this regard, the University is nurturing a culture of inclusion that promotes equality of opportunity, subscribes to diversity and upholds an environment whereby rights, accessibility to facilities, liberties and the basic dignity of all its staff, faculty and students as well as the surrounding community are accommodated and respected.

In this regard, the University through its Center for Gender Equity will continue to coordinate the process of mainstreaming diversity in the University’s academic, research and community outreach programs, projects and activities.

Strategic Initiatives

The following Strategic Initiatives shall be implemented to address UGHE resource challenges in the short, medium and long term:

Strategic Initiatives	Projected Outcome
■ Catalyze intellectual discourse and cross pollination of ideas related to gender equity and diversity inclusion at UGHE.	An enabling work environment which promotes and accommodates diversity and inclusion in all its forms
■ Mainstream gender equity and diversity inclusion	
■ Strengthen consideration for diversity and inclusion in UGHE infrastructure development	

v. Art and Culture*

5. ANNEX

a. BUDGET

UGHE Costs FY22-FY26	FY22	FY23	FY24	FY25	FY26	Total
MBBS	8,297	8,370	8,537	8,708	8,882	42,794
MGHD	3,045	3,141	3,204	3,268	3,333	15,991
Executive Education	1,704	1,767	1,803	1,839	1,876	8,989
Institute of Global Health Research Equity	528	539	549	560	571	2,747
Center for Gender Studies	871	668	629	863	881	3,912
Center for Nursing and Midwifery	286	667	782	606	619	2,960
Education Development and Quality Center	596	608	620	633	645	3,102
Arts and Culture in Global Health Public Engagement	409	417	426	434	443	2,129
Community Health and Social Medicine	173	176	180	183	187	899
Health Professions Education (HPE) Training Program	-	537	590	649	714	2,490
Total Operations expenditures	15,909	16,890	17,320	17,743	18,151	86,013
Infrastructure (Campus expansion)	18,553	16,503	4,593	-	-	39,649
Infrastructure (Butaro District Hospital expansion)	7,000	7,300	-	-	-	14,300
Infrastructure (Masaka Campus)	-	2,184	1,816	2,000	2,000	8,000
Total Capital expenditure	25,553	25,987	6,409	2,000	2,000	61,949
Total expenditure (Operations & Capital)	41,462	42,877	23,729	19,743	20,151	147,962

Kigali Heights, Plot 772 | KG 7 Ave., 5th Floor
P.O. Box 6955 | Kigali